

THE HISTORY OF THE ORIGIN OF MEDICAL TERMS AND THEIR IMPORTANCE TODAY

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Abstract. This article talks about the history of the origin and formation of medical terms. It contains information on the use of the initially formed naming of medical terms in today's consumption, their importance, and their use as interdisciplinary terms.

Key words: medical terms, phraseological phrase, origin, syndrome, communication, scientific terminology

It is difficult for a first-year student to perceive new disciplines, especially human anatomy, the study of which is impossible without knowledge of the Latin language. It, unlike other languages that we now, one way or another, use in life, has one amazing feature. On the one hand, Latin is a dead language: it went out of use around the sixth century AD and the inhabitants of no existing state use it to communicate with each other.

The Latin language has found the widest use in pharmaceuticals, medicine, and scientific terminology, so students must understand that the Latin language is a means of scientific medical communication, a means of professional communication among doctors. It is the international language of medicine, understood by doctors all over the world. Therefore, when studying medical terms, we suggest focusing on the history of their origin - this way the memorization process will be much easier and more interesting. If we analyze the etymology of Latin terms in medicine, we can come to the conclusion that many of them come from the names of certain causes that cause diseases, from proper names - for example, the names of doctors or patients. But a special group includes terms that were formed on the basis of associations with mythical characters.

In medical vocabulary, these terms are distinguished by their brightness and expressiveness. In most cases, the names of various diseases and ailments contain the names of heroes from ancient mythology. This was typical for the Renaissance, and subsequently for the New Age, when rapid changes occurred in all spheres of human activity, in particular in medicine.

One of the most memorable and colorful characters in the mythology of Ancient Greece, whose name formed the basis of the term hermaphroditism - bisexuality, is

Hermaphroditus - a stately, golden-haired young man of unearthly beauty. He rejected the nymph's love; in response, she asked the gods for eternal unity with her beloved.

In medical practice, the term Tendo Achillis (t. calcaneus) is widely used - Achilles tendon (calcaneus) - formed by the tendons of the gastrocnemius and soleus muscles of the leg, attached to the tubercle of the heel bone. It got its name from the name of the greatest of the heroes who fought at the walls of Troy, Achilles (Achilles). Fate destined him not only for great feats and immortal glory, but also for death in the prime of his life. Therefore, Achilles' mother Thetis tried to change the tragic fate of her son - she rubbed herbs with herbs, kept him in fire in order to give him immortality, and in infancy she bathed Achilles in the waters of the river

Styx, as a result of which Achilles' body became invulnerable except for the heel by which Thetis held him. But during one of the battles, fate overtook the hero - Paris, with the help of Apollo, hit Achilles with an arrow in the heel, after which he fell dead after some time. This case served as the source for the emergence of the frequently used phraseological phrase "Achilles tendon." The name of another no less famous hero, the giant Atlas, who holds the entire weight of the sky on his mighty back, is associated with the name of the first cervical vertebra atlas, atlantis, m. When studying the anatomy of the nervous system, you can come across the term, arachnoid membrane of the brain - arachnoidea mater cerebri, it is covered with a network of small grooves of nerves, the appearance of which resembles a spider's web.

This term appeared thanks to one of the daring heroines who challenged the gods, Arachne. Arachne had no equal in the skill of weaving. She spun threads like fog into fabrics as transparent as air. In Greek, "arachne" means spider. The name of the goddess of love Venus is associated with the name of venereal diseases - sexually transmitted diseases. In medicine, there is also such a term as pomum Adami seu prominentia laryngea Adam's apple or laryngeal protrusion, on the front surface of the neck, mostly in men. The term cornu Ammonis (hippocampus) The cornu of Ammon is sometimes called the hippocampus, a part of the old cerebral cortex that forms one of the walls of the lateral ventricle. In our opinion, the term "head of Medusa" - caput Medusae - seemed most interesting. This is what doctors call the characteristic pattern formed when the subcutaneous veins of the anterior abdominal wall are dilated, visible to the naked eye, which is caused by congestion in the portal vein during collateral circulation. The similarity of this design with the snake-headed hair on the head of Medusa the Gorgon was the reason for the creation of this term.

A large number of mythological terms are found in psychology - the science of the psyche, mental activity of a person, his soul. The main source of their occurrence is the myths of Ancient Greece - for example, narcissism and pygmalionism, venerophobia and

nymphomania. But the creation of the term Ondine's curse syndrome is based on a beautiful old German legend. The mermaid Ondine fell in love with the knight Lawrence, he reciprocated her feelings, and the lovers decided to get married. At the altar, Lawrence swore an oath to Ondine that he would remain faithful to her as long as he breathed upon waking each morning. Over the years, the beautiful girl lost her attractiveness, and her lover became cold towards her. One day Ondine saw her husband with someone else and cursed him out of resentment. Now he could only breathe while awake. If he falls asleep, his breathing will stop. So this syndrome means that a person stops breathing during sleep. A new round in the development of terminological vocabulary in psychology occurred in the 20th century.

This is due to the emergence of psychoanalysis by Sigmund Freud, who, to substantiate his teachings, often resorted to the myth of the Argonauts, as well as the Theban cycle of myths. The fate and character of their characters - Oedipus, Antigone, Medea, Jocasta, Orestes, Phaedrus and Electra - Freud carefully analyzed and transferred to his patients. For example, the Oedipus complex is sexual attraction to a parent of the opposite sex. In the Theban cycle of myths, Oedipus, without knowing it, married his mother, and they had children.

When the truth about Oedipus's origins was revealed, his mother committed suicide, and the hero himself blinded himself and set off to wander the world. Such clinical terms as Polycrates complex, Cain complex, Io syndrome, Persephone syndrome, Midas syndrome, etc. are known. Why is it so important to know the history of the development of terminology, the history of the creation of medical terms.

First of all, this will broaden the student's horizons; it will be easier for him to assimilate and comprehend these terms, and with them the phenomena that correspond to them. Which will subsequently lead to a deep understanding of the diagnostic meaning of clinical terms, to the development of clinical thinking, which will undoubtedly help future doctors in their professional activities.

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